

Incorporating tracer particles for DVC of fibre-reinforced composites

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Composites: Multiscale, hierarchical materials

Macroscale
Structure

Microscale
Constituents

Mesoscale
Ply - Laminate

Swolfs et al.

From digital images...

Undeformed image

Deformed image

...to digital volumes

Undeformed
Volume

Deformed
Volume

Strain
Field

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The need for heterogeneity

Intrinsic, temporally stable, microstructural variation

Absent in conventional polymers

Insufficient in the fibre-direction of composites Schöberl et al.

Choosing the tracer particle

Incorporating the tracer particle

Ensuring mechanically consistent materials

Securing a suitable microstructure for DVC

From localised dispersion...

SEM

ROI: $60 \times 60 \mu\text{m}^2$

Screening

High-resolution XCT

Voxel size: 500 nm

VOI: $500 \times 500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^3$

Analysis of all clusters

...to globalised dispersion

Low-resolution XCT

Voxel size: 25 μm

VOI: 10 \times 10 \times 50 mm^3

Analysis of **large** clusters

The presence of a multiscale speckle pattern

How uniform is the speckle pattern?

What about the mechanical representativity

Tension

What about the mechanical representativity

Compression

What about the rheological representativity

0-shear viscosity

Are the particles essential?

Virtual Displacement study Mehdikhani et al.

Applied strain $\varepsilon = 0.02$ (2%)

Longitudinal (Y)

Transverse (X)

Summary and Future

- Particle incorporation for DVC of composites
- Quantification of dispersion
- Optimisation of particle type, volume fraction
- Investigation of mechanical and rheological behaviour

Heterogeneity

Uniformity

Efficiency

Representativity

ESRF ID16B

- In-situ experiments on multi-fibre and single-fibre
- BaTiO₃ and TiC fiducials
- From Carbon to Glass fibres

Carbon

Glass

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Thank you for your attention

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